

FROM TEXT TO CONTEXT: THE ROLE OF REALIA IN THEODORE DREISER'S NOVELS

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Annotation: This article explores the intricate use of realia and sociolinguistic elements in Theodore Dreiser's novels, particularly focusing on "Sister Carrie" and "An American Tragedy." Dreiser's narrative incorporates a rich lexicon of realia—specifically names, street names, and cultural landmarks—that reflects the socio-economic conditions and urban landscape of late 19th and early 20th century America. By examining these linguocultural elements, the study highlights how Dreiser not only depicts the environmental backdrop but also embeds deeper societal and cultural narratives within his works. The research delves into the role of realia as tools for sociocultural and historical representation, analyzing how these elements enhance the narrative's authenticity and depth. Additionally, the challenges of translating these culturally loaded terms into other languages, such as Uzbek, are discussed, underscoring the complexities of maintaining the original text's cultural and historical nuances. This study contributes to the understanding of naturalist literature and its capacity to reveal insights into the socio-cultural dynamics of its era, providing a nuanced perspective on the interaction between language, culture, and identity in literary texts.

Key words: Theodore Dreiser, naturalist literature, linguocultural realism, realia in literature, socio-economic conditions, urban landscape, cultural translation, sociolinguistics, narrative authenticity.

Introduction

The modern study of literature often traverses beyond mere narrative analysis to examine the deeper cultural, societal, and linguistic underpinnings within texts. Theodore Dreiser's works, especially "Sister Carrie" and "An American Tragedy," serve as exemplars of this literary exploration, as they provide rich insights into the socio-economic and cultural landscapes of the late 19th and early 20th centuries in the United States. This introduction aims to frame Dreiser's work within the broader context of cultural and linguistic studies, particularly through the lens of

linguocultural realism and the depiction of societal realities via the use of realia words—terms that encapsulate the essence of the time and place they describe.

Dreiser, a figure synonymous with the American naturalist movement, embedded his narratives with a dense tapestry of realia that offer a window into the era's socio-cultural and economic conditions. His characters navigate through a world marked by rapid urbanization, industrialization, and a burgeoning class consciousness, all of which are reflected in the lexicon of the times. For instance, the streets of Chicago in "Sister Carrie" are not merely backdrop settings but are integral to understanding the urban landscape that influenced the novel's characters and their interactions. The references to specific locales like Fifth Avenue and Van Buren Street go beyond geographical markers; they signify the economic and social stratification prevalent during Dreiser's era.

This study delves into the historical significance of these locales within Dreiser's works, underscoring how linguocultural elements such as street names, restaurants, and other urban landmarks played a pivotal role in the narrative structure. These elements are not just narrative tools but are imbued with cultural and historical significance that reflects the broader societal changes of the time. For example, Rector's Restaurant, a locale frequented by Dreiser's characters, was not just a dining establishment but a social hub that mirrored the changing dynamics of class and luxury in early 20th century America.

Moreover, the analysis of realia extends to the anthropological aspects of the language used in Dreiser's novels. Names, as socially marked lexical units, reveal much about the social identity and cultural affiliations of the characters. The names Clyde Griffiths and Sondra Finchley, among others, are not arbitrary; they carry deep societal implications and reflect the characters' social status and cultural heritage. This linguistic examination offers insights into how names function as centers of social force, encapsulating personal and communal histories.

The relevance of this study is further accentuated by the modern scholarly interest in the interaction between language and culture, particularly in the translation of culturally specific parts of texts. The challenges of translating Dreiser's work, especially the realia, into other languages such as Uzbek demonstrate the intricate interplay between language and culture. This not only highlights the difficulties

inherent in preserving the cultural and historical context in translation but also emphasizes the importance of these elements in understanding the text's full depth.

This introduction sets the stage for a comprehensive examination of Dreiser's use of linguocultural elements within his novels. It aims to explore how these elements serve not merely as narrative devices but as crucial components of the social fabric that Dreiser sought to depict. By analyzing how these linguocultural markers are woven into the narrative, this study endeavors to reveal the complex interrelations between individual identities and broader cultural dynamics, providing a richer understanding of Dreiser's literary and cultural contributions. This approach not only enhances our appreciation of Dreiser's work but also contributes to the broader field of literary studies, offering a nuanced view of how literature can serve as a mirror to the historical and cultural realities of its time.

Main part: Theodore Herman Albert Dreiser (German Theodore Herman Albert Dreiser) (August 27, 1871, Terre Haute, Indiana, USA - December 28, 1945, Hollywood, California, USA) was an American writer, journalist and public figure. Communist. A prominent representative of the American current of naturalism and critical realism. Dreiser's work had a great influence on American culture of the 20th century, the appearance of each of his novels caused a stormy response in American literary criticism. Theodore Dreiser's most famous works: "Sister Carrie"

Language serves as a means of communication between peoples, a way of transmitting their cultural and moral values. Vocabulary is very vulnerable in any nation, significant changes occur very often, changing the linguistic composition of the language.

As a result, there are words-realities. Realia words are part of the background knowledge, i. e. , the totality of ideas about what constitutes the background against which the life of another people, another country takes place [1, p. 130].

The history of cities can be traced not only in specially designed literature, but also in novels, poems, and letters from the authors of those times, i. e. authentic materials, representing a huge source of knowledge. T. Dreiser's novel "Sister Carrie" is a rich source of linguoculturally rich words, value words, word realities, such as onomastic realities, ethnographic realities (i. e. realities denoting food, clothes), realities from the field of culture and art, geographical realities, etc.

The study of the onomastic realities of the city of Chicago in the 19th century is of great interest. First, the modern image of the city of Chicago is very different from the historical version of the city. Secondly, the city of Chicago has gained worldwide attention as one of the leading tourist cities. Thirdly, Chicago is a city that set an example for the whole world in the construction of skyscrapers, which was not observed in the 19th century, since it was at this time that the formation of the city began. In the XIX century, Chicago became a developed city, as a result of which it attracted a large number of people. "In 1889 Chicago had the peculiar qualification of growth" [2, p. 12]. In the words of Carl Sandburg "Chicago-city with broad shoulders" ['City of broad shoulders'] [2, p. 12].

And at present, Chicago is the third largest city in the United States (after New York and Los Angeles), the second most important financial center of the country and the largest transport hub in North America. Located on the southwest coast of Lake Michigan in Illinois; the county seat of Cook County.

Chicago is often referred to as "The Second City" or "Windy City", the "second city" refers to economic leadership, and the nickname "Windy City" he received because of the fluctuations of city power. Street names are represented in Sister Carrie's work: Fifth Avenue, Van Buren Street, Halstead Street, Jackson Street, etc. Next, consider some of them. For example, "In passing through Fifth Avenue, south towards Van Buren Street. . ." [2, p. 12].

Van Buren Street is a tunnel that allows you to get to the business center of the city in the shortest possible time. Passing under the Chicago River [Chicago River], Cowperwood (an American businessman) was the founder of the construction of this tunnel, he bought a significant piece of land north of the bridge and thus was able to start work without hindrance. In addition, we come across a description of restaurants, "Rector's restaurant" [3, p. 35] - a well-known restaurant that attracted people from the upper strata of society. ". . . rector's with polished marble walls and floor, its profusion of lights, its show of china and silverware, and above all, its reputation as a resort for actors. . ."

HENRY VOIGT (a member of the Ephemera Society, Grolier Club, Library Company of Philadelphia, and Delaware Bibliophiles) wrote: [4, p. 45] "Rector's is one of the most important restaurants in American social history". David Kamp in The New York Times wrote: "George Rector generated a lot of hype, providing the

press with highly-exaggerated accounts of his restaurant and its clientele, such as the legendary gourmand “Diamond Jim” Brady. Indeed, in the novel by T. Dreiser, the restaurant acts as a luxury item that does not allow an ordinary person to visit a "fairy tale". So, for example, dinner in a restaurant cost about \$20, which is about \$520 today, only a noble person could afford to have a bite to eat in such an institution.

Based on historical facts, it is worth noting that George Rector considered it necessary to keep up with the times: “In fact, the menu appears to be out of step with the times, featuring upper-class dishes of the nineteenth century” [5, p. 29]. Thanks to the famous restaurant, which brought great benefits of its owner, in 1910-1913 a hotel was built bearing the name "Rector Hotel" [5, p. 29]. It should be noted that restaurants for the middle class of the population were no less popular. „ . . old windsor dining-room, which was then a large, comfortable place, with an excellent cuisine and substantial service. . . ” [6, p. 69].

Here was the great Fair store with its multitude of delivery wagons about its long window display, its crowd of shoppers. . . ” [7, p. 81]. “. . . great Fair store” a bazaar that allows people to buy household items, clothes at an inexpensive price. The bazaar can be found in every city, most often it is a crowded place.

For the first time the market appeared in 1874, Illinois. The bazaar got its name thanks to Ernst J. Lehmann (Founder), he described the market with the following words: "the store was like a fair because it offered many different things for sale at a cheap price"[8, p. 33]. In modern society, the concept of "market" is part of the vocabulary of a person, for people of the twenty-first century, the market is a place of retail in the open air or in the mall.

The culture of the population of the city of Chicago also became more educated and aesthetically developed, as a result, theaters appeared. ". . . theatres, Mr. Frank A. Hale, manager of the Standard theatre. . . ” The Standard theater is a popular theater that opened in 1913, the original name of the theater was “Immenhausen’s Theatre” [9, p. 103], but after a while it got a different name. The theater was owned by Burt Ross, Joel Ross and Edward Ross, businessmen of the time.

The theater was located on Clark Street at Chicago venue, in Chicago’s Near North Side neighborhood. In 1960, the theater ceased to exist, but already in 1969 the building was reconstructed and restored, instead of the theater, the cinema [the Le

Image Cinema] opened its doors. Today, the building is used as a liquor store, which is a hit with the Chicago populace due to the history of the building.

What is really important is that two centuries later, the names of the streets from the novel by T. Dreiser have retained their name to this day. ". . . he had selected in East Adams Street, and thereafter they took a cab to what was then a pleasant evening resort out on Cottage Grove Avenue near 39th Street. . . ." [10, p. 157].

East Adams Street was built between 1890-1930 and attracted attention due to the Victorian style of the houses. East Adams Street – an infamous and wonderful road in Maycomb, Illinois. It is the biggest party street in the mid-west, as it borders Western Illinois University and has the majority of the schools frat houses on it. Adams street is a historic district that is one of five historic districts on the National Register in the city of Franklin. Adams Street is also designated as a local historic district of the city, making it a subject of admiration [11].

We can see the anthroponoms and toponyms are translated by the means of transliteration and transcription methods:

Clyde Griffiths- Klayd Griffits

Hortense- Hortense

Samuel- Samuel

Sondra Finchley- Sondra Finchley

Roberta- Roberta

Gilbert- Gilbert

Lycurgus-Likurg

New York- Nyu-York

To some extent, the names reflect people's lives, beliefs, goals, occupations, attitudes toward the outside world, artistic inventiveness, and even historical contacts. Names are centers of social force. It is claimed that a country's health is determined by its attitude toward names. A person's name and surname are a type of social marker that is valued. A name is always social, and not having a name is also a social indicator.

The name frequently had a prominent social trait and was employed in a specific social setting. A legitimate name is associated with a person's physical and spiritual identity. The name, as part of self-consciousness, affects a person's value orientations in his demands for recognition, the features of gender identity, the nature of

developing life prospects, and the system of rights and duties in ontogenesis. Anthroponyms, as socially marked lexical units (hereafter LE), have a unique position in the process of language and culture interaction. Anthroponyms represent the history, religion beliefs, and culture community to which they belong, accumulating a large quantity of nationally significant data. The focus of this study is on national lama anthroponyms in English Theodore Dreiser novels (*An American Tragedy* - 1925 and *The Financier* - 1912), in which the action takes place in two separate cultural communities in the United States. The importance of the subject is related, on the one hand, to the increased interest in aspects of Islamic culture in the modern world, and on the other hand, it is a required chance to explore ways of translating culturally specific parts of material.

The exploration of Theodore Dreiser's use of realia in his novels "Sister Carrie" and "An American Tragedy" provides profound insights into the intersection of language, culture, and society in the context of early 20th-century America. Dreiser's detailed depiction of the urban landscape through the meticulous use of realia not only serves to anchor his narratives in a specific socio-cultural milieu but also enhances the realism that is characteristic of his writing style. This study has demonstrated that the names, street names, and landmarks depicted in his works do more than simply set a scene; they encapsulate the economic, social, and cultural dynamics of the era, offering readers a gateway into the historical context of the time.

Through the analysis of Dreiser's linguistic choices, this research highlights the critical role of realia as both a narrative technique and a cultural commentary. These elements in Dreiser's texts act as socio-cultural markers that reflect and critique the American dream, class struggle, and the transformative impacts of urbanization and industrialization. The detailed examination of how specific terms and references are used helps to illustrate the broader societal issues Dreiser sought to address, including the complexities of social mobility and the often harsh realities of capitalist society.

Moreover, the challenges associated with translating these culturally and historically specific elements into other languages underscore the intricate relationship between language and culture. This aspect of the study emphasizes the importance of sensitive and informed translation practices that respect the original's context while making it accessible to a global audience. It is evident that maintaining the integrity of the original text's cultural depth requires a nuanced understanding of both the source and target languages.

In conclusion, Theodore Dreiser's incorporation of realia in his literature not only enriches his narrative but also serves as a crucial tool for cultural transmission and historical documentation. His works provide a canvas that reflects the American societal changes of his time, making them invaluable resources for understanding the past. The findings of this study contribute to the broader discourse on the role of literature in cultural and historical representation, affirming the value of literary studies in unraveling the complex layers of human experience and societal development. This underscores the enduring relevance of Dreiser's work in American literary scholarship and highlights the ongoing need to explore the dynamic interplay between a society's language and its cultural identity.

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